

Tax Policies and Performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study focused on the impact of taxation policies on the growth and performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The research adopted survey design. The population comprised the entire 7468 SMEs in Ibadan, Nigeria. The simple random sampling technique was used to choose the SMEs owners in Ibadan. The data was collected by administering the questionnaire and data collected were analyzed using descriptive and linear regression techniques. Findings showed that there is a significant negative relationship between higher tax rates and the profitability of SMEs in Ibadan, a significant positive relationship between tax incentives and the investment decisions of SMEs in Ibadan and a significant positive relationship between efficient tax administration and the growth and sustainability of SMEs. Based on the above findings, this study concludes that there is a significant relationship between taxation policies and the growth of SMEs in Ibadan. The study therefore recommended that tax regulations governing SMEs should be simplified in order to make compliance easier for them. This includes clear and simple tax regulations, and an undemanding tax filing process and also there should be provision of educational programs and workshops to help SMEs understand their tax obligations and navigate the tax system effectively.

Keywords: Banking Sector, First Bank, IFRS, Financial Reporting Quality, Compliance

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Introduction

As an indispensable tool of the government, taxation helps facilitate and regulate general economic activities in a country. It is the compulsory levies imposed by the government on business profits, personal income, dividends, and commissions necessary for the infrastructural and social development of the country (Tabet & Onyeukwu, 2019). It has three main objectives: raising revenue for government expenditure, controlling the economy and economic activities, and regulating income and employment. These objectives specifically include raising revenue, reducing inequality in the economy, regulating the consumption of certain goods, curbing inflation, servicing the national debt, planning and directing the economy, protecting infant industries, promoting exports and curtailing imports, and maintaining credit balance (Njoku, 2009; Babalola, Oyedokun, & Adeyemo, 2019).

Some basic principles otherwise known as tax policies guide the tax system and practice, without which it will not operate efficiently and effectively. A poorly executed tax system may lead to poor

efficiency, high collection charges, waste of time for the taxpayer and the staff, insufficient tax revenue and the deviation of optimum allocation of resources (Ocheni, 2015; Oyedokun, Akintoye, & Salawu, 2018).

Concurrently, SMEs are catalysts for national economic growth and development. Also, the SMEs sector is considered important to enhance the private sector contribution and provides the critical building blocks for industrialization and sustainable economic growth (Udechukwu, 2003; Taiwo, & Oyedokun, 2022).

The Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of any major developed economy, as well as important contributors to employment, economic and export growth. It was opined that SMEs remain the foundation as well as the building block in the realization of any meaningful and sustainable growth in an economy and constitute the driving force in the attainment of industrial growth and development (Agwu, 2014). This is basically due to their great potential in ensuring diversification and expansion of industrial production as well as the attainment of the basic objectives of growth. For sustainable economy, SMEs have been stressed as capable of helping in bringing about positive economic turn around and complementing the effort of the existing large scales industries (Udofot & Etim, 2017; Oyedokun & Ayinde, 2023). Small and Medium-scale Enterprises (SMEs) are some of the most authentic drivers of sustainable development, especially in emerging economies.

A researcher opined that the recognition of the importance of the roles of the SMEs as the pillar of growth has prompted the increased attention and specific education on the method and approach to build and sustain a truly viable private sector dominated by small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) not only in Nigeria but also in other developing and developed economies (Peace, Ajike & Ezejiolor, 2017; Onigbinde, & Oyedokun, 2023).

These SMEs contribute to long-run industrial growth by producing an increasing number of businesses that grow out of the small-scale level of business development. In Nigeria, the government is advocating for an increase in the growth rate of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), a stable general price level, increased employment opportunities, etc. through the establishment of SMEs.

However, these cannot be realized if effective programmes, especially regarding taxation practices, are not established and implemented to encourage sustainable business growth and development. Taxation practices are essentially those multiple payments obligations placed on SMEs by the state. Taxation/taxing practices on SMEs coupled with inadequate provision of social infrastructure poses a threat that these businesses may not be able to survive the harsh economic condition. Often, it results in a reduction of their operating capacity and the worst scenario, their failure. Recognizing the enormous potential contributions of SMEs to economic growth and development, concerning the strategic role taxation plays in facilitating the affairs of governments, one is tempted to ask if the taxation practices on SMEs have a desirable or undesirable effect on the operational capacity of SMEs.

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of taxation policies on the growth and performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Assess the effect of tax rates on the financial performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.
2. Investigate the influence of tax incentives on the investment decisions of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.
3. Analyze the role of tax administration efficiency in the growth and sustainability of SMEs.

Literature Review

Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) have been identified as the catalysts for economic growth and national development for both developed and developing countries. They are globally recognised as engines of Socio-economic transformation. Its roles in the national economy cannot be over-emphasised as they are very important part of the Nigerian economy. They are also recognised by the economic development institutions in Nigeria as the largest segment of economy. Small and Medium scale Enterprises contribute much higher proportion to Gross Domestic Product in some developing and developed countries than currently observed in Nigeria. SME contribute 51% of GDP in USA, 51% of GDP in South Korea, 81% of GDP in Morocco and 57% GDP in Australia (Al-Abri, Abdul Rahim & Hussain, 2018; Oyedokun & Sorinmade, 2023).

The Monetary Policy Circular No. 22 of 1988 of the Central Bank of Nigeria defined small-scale enterprises as enterprises whose annual turnover was not more than N500, 000. In the 1990 budget, the Federal Government of Nigeria defined small-scale enterprises for purposes of commercial bank loans as those with an annual turnover

not exceeding N500,000, and for Merchant Bank Loans, those enterprises with capital investments not exceeding 2 million naira (excluding cost of land) or a maximum of N 5 million. The National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) put the ceiling for small-scale industries at N10 million. Section 37b (2) of the Companies and Allied Matters Decree of 1990 defines a small company as one with an annual turnover of not more than N 2 million and net asset value of not more than 1 million naira. (Ekpenyong & Nyong, 1992). The Small and Medium Enterprise Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS) sees the SME as “any enterprise with a maximum asset base of N500 million (excluding land and working capital), and with no lower or upper limit of staff”.

Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria, [SMEDAN] defined Medium Enterprises as a business employing 1 to 200 persons while micro businesses employ 1-9 persons, and small businesses employ 50-199 persons. Small and Medium Scale enterprises in other developing countries have indicated that countries with a larger share of SMEs employment have higher economic growth. It is suggested that one of the significant characteristics of a flourishing and growing economy is a booming and blooming SMEs sector. It is a well-known fact that SMEs play vital roles in the economic growth and development of any nation. Its roles are well pronounced in creating employment, addressing the impediments of poverty, reducing inequalities and efficient utilization of local resources (SMEDAN, 2012).

Taxation Policies

In every country, the existing governmental policies have the potential to affect the operation as well as the performance of every business. Such impacts can be explained from the technical point of view. Based on this perspective, specific governmental policies that can have direct or indirect effects on businesses include taxation, subsidies, interest rates and exchange rates. Government taxation policy has been widely recognized as one factor that can affect the performance of every business. For instance, the imposition of high taxes on specific imported products will ultimately encourage local businesses to produce more such goods (Oyedokun & Onigbinde, 2024).

The term taxation is derived from tax(es) described as a compulsory or mandatory levy charged by any authority or government on individuals or corporate income with a view to generating revenue for the provision of goods, services, and other social development to the citizenry. "Tax is very necessary if government or authorities must embark on the provision of basic amenities and social services through capital projects like; construction of roads, building of bridges, airports, hospitals, construction of seaports, dams, provision of recreational centers, motor-parks, markets, among others. These obligations require huge financial budget and resources by government to be able to undertake and deliver on time (Etim, Nsima & Damel, 2020; Aina, Aderibigbe, Adigun, & Oyedokun, 2017). These activities would have to be funded by the government through different sources of funds and financing prominent of which is taxation, which comes in different forms and types. The National Tax Policy defines tax as "a financial charge or levy imposed upon an individual or legal entity by a state or a legal entity of the state; it is a pecuniary burden laid upon individuals or property to support government expenditure" (NTP, 2010; Aderibigbe, Oke, & Oyedokun, 2017). On the other hand, taxation is the act of assessing, imposing and collecting various taxes. It is concerned with the administration of tax policy geared towards the assessment, collection and accounting for the tax revenues to the government by the authority saddled with the responsibility.

Taxation and SMEs Taxes

Taxation is a critical component of running a business in Nigeria, as it provides the government with the necessary revenue to fund public fund public services and infrastructure. For small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in particular, understanding and properly managing tax obligations is essential for ensuring compliance and avoiding penalties (Resolution Law firm, nd; Oloyede, Kupoluyi, Oyedokun, & Benjamin, 2017).

SMEs in Nigeria are subject to a range of federal, state and local government taxes, including:

Federal Taxes

Company Income Tax (CIT): Administered by the Federal Inland Revenue Service, this tax is levied on the profits of companies operating in Nigeria, including SMEs. The standard corporate income tax rate is 30%, but SMEs with an annual turnover of N25 million or less may qualify for lower rates or exemptions (Leadership News, nd; Mlanga, & Oyedokun, 2018).

Value Added Tax (VAT): Value Added Tax is a consumption tax applied to the sale of goods and services. The current VAT rate in Nigeria is 7.5%. SMEs that meet the registration threshold are

responsible for collecting VAT from customers and remitting it to the Federal Inland Revenue Service (Trybrass, nd).

Education Tax: All registered companies in Nigeria are required to pay 2% of their assessable profit as education tax to the Education Tax Fund (Leadership News, nd).

Stamp Duty: Stamp Duty is a tax levied on legal documents, such as contracts, and agreements. The stamp duty rate varies depending on the type of document.

Custom Duties and Excise Taxes: SMEs involved in the importation of goods are subject to customs duties, which are taxes on imported goods. The rates vary based on the type of goods imported. Excise taxes may also apply to certain locally manufactured goods.

State Taxes

Personal Income Tax (PIT)

All small business owners are liable to pay their personal income tax which is governed by the Personal Income Tax Act (Cap P8 LFN 2004), for each year of assessment from their source of income for the year, which also includes the profit made in the small business. It is paid as a direct assessment which is applicable to sole proprietors (small business) owners. The tax is paid from the income earned in the preceding year without notice or demand from the relevant tax authority. Although the collection of this form of tax is the federal responsibility, it is however collected by the state government through the State Inland Revenue Service (SIRS) (Resolution Law firm, nd; Ajose, & Oyedokun, 2018).

Business Premises Tax: This tax is levied by state governments on properties used for business purposes, such as offices, factories, and shops. The tax rate varies by state and location (urban or rural).

Development Levy: Some states may impose a development levy on businesses to fund local infrastructure and development projects.

Local Government Taxes

Levies and Rates: local government authorities may impose various levies and rates on businesses, such as shop and kiosk rates, motor park levies, and public convenience fees.

Tax Incentives

Tax incentives have been defined in various ways by different scholars. Tax incentives have been described as exemption or reliefs granted to an individual or a company to reduce the effect of taxation and thus encourage savings and investment. It was noted further that the reality of tax incentives in Nigeria is that not many people truly take advantage of the incentives that exist, and even when they do, past trends have suggested an individual corporate approach rather than an industry-wide approach (Okauru, 2009; Oyedokun, Fowokan, Akintoye, & Hassan, 2018). Also, Keen (2013) defined tax incentives as all measures and strategies which provide for more favourable tax treatment to a certain activities or sector, and he went on to describe the following to be typical tax

incentives: tax holidays which is defined as the temporal exemption of business investment from certain specified taxes, typically at least corporate income tax. Partial tax holidays offer the reduced obligations rather than full exemption, special zones which are placed in geographically limited areas where qualified companies can locate and hence benefit from the exemption of various scopes of taxes or administrative requirements, investment tax credit which is the deduction of some fraction of an investment from the tax liability, investments allowance/accelerated depreciation which is the deduction of some fraction of an investment from taxable profits (in addition to depreciation), reduced tax rates/preferential tax rates which are the reductions in a tax rate, specifically the corporate income tax rate, exemptions from various taxes which are the exemptions from certain taxes, most of the time those collected at the border such as tariffs, excises and VAT on imported inputs, financing incentives which are the reductions in tax rates for the funds providers for example: the reduced withholding taxes on dividends and loss carried forward which is usually offered when the business makes a loss, the loss can be carried forward to offset the future (Olaniyi, Ajayi, & Oyedokun, 2018).

Tax Administration and Business Growth

Tax administration plays a crucial role in promoting business growth by providing a stable and predictable tax environment. The theoretical framework for understanding the impact of tax administration on business growth is rooted in the concept of tax compliance. Tax compliance refers to the willingness of businesses to comply with tax laws and regulations. Tax administration can influence tax compliance by providing a clear and consistent tax environment, reducing tax evasion, and promoting transparency and accountability. Numerous studies have examined the impact of tax administration on business growth, with varying results. A seminal study found that a 1 percentage point increase in the corporate tax rate was associated with a 0.5% decrease in firm-level investment (Devereux & Griffith, 1998; Oyedokun, Fowokan, Akintoye, & Dada, 2018). Similarly, another study found that a 1 percentage point increase in the corporate tax rate was associated with a 0.3% decrease in firm-level investment (Hines & Rice, 1997). Building on these findings, there was an investigation on the impact of tax administration on foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic growth in developing countries. Their results indicated that effective tax administration can significantly increase FDI and promote economic growth (Klemm & Van Parys, 2012; Umar-Dauda, & Oyedokun, 2018).

Focusing specifically on SMEs, the role of firm size in the relationship between tax rates and investment was examined. The findings suggested that the negative impact of high tax rates on investment was more pronounced for smaller firms, as they often have fewer resources and less flexibility to adapt to changes in the tax environment (Egger & Raff, 2015; Fowokan, Oyedokun, & Abdul, 2018).

Theoretical Review

Ability to Pay Theory

In its use for assessing the efficiency of taxes and appraising fiscal policy, the benefit to pay theory was initially developed by Knut Wicksell in 1896 and Eric Lindahl in 1919, who were economists of the Stockholm School. The theory was later extended in the work of Paul Samuelson and

Richard Musgrave. This theory states that one should be taxed according to the ability to pay. It is simply an attempt to maximize an explicit value judgement about the distributive effects of taxes (Afshari, Ardabili & Ali, 2012). This approach considers tax liability in its true form, that is, compulsory payment to the state without quid pro quo. It does not assume any commercial or semi-commercial relationship between the state and the citizens. The basic assumption of this theory is that the burden of taxation should be shared by the members of society on the principles of justice and equity and that these principles necessitate that the tax burden is apportioned according to their relative ability to pay. Both theorists opined that if the objective of the government is to redistribute income, it should set taxes according to the ability-to-pay principle. A researcher argued against the ability to pay theory where he opined that a citizen is to pay taxes just because he can and his relative share in the total tax burden is to be determined by his relative paying capacity (Bhartia, 2009). This doctrine has been in vogue for at least as long as the benefits theory. This theory was supported by socialist thinkers because of its conformity with the ideas and concepts of justice and equity. The doctrine also received equally strong support from non-socialist thinkers also and became a part of the theory of welfare economics.

However, this theory was a subject of criticism. The critic opined that it is difficult to measure ability. There are, in general, three measures of ability: income, expenditure and property which are (i) income which is said to be a better measure of ability than wealth; (ii) expenditure, expenditure is the best possible measure of ability. He advocated an expenditure tax which was tried in India for some time but withdrawn subsequently. A poor man may spend more if he has more dependents and if he must look after his old parents. So, his expenditure may be higher than his colleague belonging to the same income bracket. But his expenditure does not reflect his true ability to pay and (iii) property, it is believed that possession of wealth or property is a reflection of well-being, but to a limited degree. For example, if two people have the same amount of wealth, they are not equally well-off. One may have some productive wealth like a building which yields a steady income. Another may have unproductive wealth (i.e., jewelry) of the same value. Naturally, their ability to pay taxes will differ greatly.

Empirical Review

Ojeka (2011) carried out by on tax policy and the growth of SMEs and its implications for the Nigerian economy, it was discovered that the lower the amount of taxes paid by SMEs, the higher the amount of growth-related investments the profits are used for. The study, therefore, concluded that for SMEs to flourish, an appropriate tax policy that will not be an impediment to SMEs and which will enhance voluntary compliance should be put in place. This position was supported by Ojochogwu and Ojeka (2012), in their study titled, the relationship between tax policy, growth of SMEs and the Nigerian economy. The study revealed that the higher the amount of tax paid by SMEs, the lower the funds available for re-investment and this, therefore, leads to a slow rate of business expansion.

Ocheni (2015) conducted a study on impact analysis of tax policy and the performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigerian economy in which he concluded that the best tax policy for SMEs is one that lowers compliance and administrative costs, reduces uncertainty faced by taxpayers, and improves the level of voluntary compliance. He, therefore, among other

recommendations, stated that tax policies should be designed in a manner that will encourage those who are potential taxpayers, voluntary compliance and these will eventually lead to expansion of existing business interests of the SMEs in Nigeria. Assessing the effect of multiple taxations on SMEs' performance in Benue State using the survey design, it was postulated by Ocheni and Gemade (2015) in their study that multiple taxations affect the growth and survival of SMEs in Benue state. They, therefore, among other recommendations, stated the need for SMEs to be levied lower amounts of taxes to ensure that they have enough funds to carry out activities that will result in their growth. Estimating the effect of tax payment on the performance of SMEs in Ghana West Municipal Assembly, Tee, Boadi and Opoku (2016) using several analytical tools such as correlation, regression, amongst others, discovered that the higher the tax incentives towards SMEs, the lesser the negative influence of tax on purchases made by them. The same study also established that SMEs are not aware of tax reliefs by the government towards them and therefore these reliefs were found to have an insignificant effect on the profitability of SMEs.

Twesige and Gasheja (2019) analyzed in a study that the effect of tax incentives on the growth of sales of SMEs from 2013 up to 2018 in Kenya, where the sales were said to be increasing year to year. Based on these results from the sampled SMEs financial statements, the financial performance of the SMEs was good. Since profitability is said to be a measure of the amount by which a company's revenue exceeds its relevant expenses, the results of their study revealed that the availability of tax incentives led to an increase in sales during the study period. This means that tax incentives have a positive effect on the growth of sales of SMEs. The findings relate to the study carried out by Klter and Demirgne (2007), who pointed out that sales revenue and profitability of SMES are affected significantly by tax incentives.

Mayende (2013) analyzed the effects of tax incentives on the performance of Ugandan manufacturing firms in terms of gross sales and value-added employing panel data estimation techniques. The study findings show that firms with tax incentives perform better in terms of gross sales growth and value added than their counterparts. The study thus concluded that Government needs to streamline the provision of tax incentives for better firm performance.

Issac (2015) investigated the effects of government taxation policy on Uasin Gishu County, Kenya SMEs sales revenue. The study adopted an exploratory research design. The data for the study were generated from secondary and primary sources, the primary data were extracted by administering 180 questionnaires, personal interviews and document analysis. The research findings showed that government tax policy has a direct significant impact on SMEs sales revenue. Furthermore, the study revealed that the effects of the government taxation policy on SMEs sales revenue could either be positive or negative. The study concluded that the SMEs should be levied lower amount of tax payable in order to allow for them to have as much as necessary funds for other activities that will lead to growth in their business and yield profitability.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. The population comprised the entire 7468 SMEs in Ibadan, Nigeria. The simple random sampling technique was used to choose the SMEs owners in Ibadan. The research employed Taro Yamane's method to get the sample size, which is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n= sample size

N = Study population

e = level of significance. This study adopts a 5% level of significance.

Operationalizing the formula, the sample size was calculated as:

$$n = \frac{7468}{1 + 7468(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{7468}{18.7}$$

$$n = 399 \text{ respondents.} + \text{ error} = 299$$

The data was collected by administering the questionnaire and data collected were analyzed using descriptive and linear regression techniques.

Results and Presentation of Data

Table 1: Analysis of Demographic Data of Respondents

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Number of Employees in the Business	1-100	3	3.0
	101-200	16	16.0
	More than 200	81	81.0
	Total	100	100
Number of Years Business Operation	Less than 1 year	14	14
	1-3 years	22	22
	4-6 years	23	23
	7-10 years	19	19
	More than 10 years	22	22
	Total	100	100
Sector of Business	Manufacturing	39	39
	Services	17	17
	Retail	18	18
	Agriculture	13	13
	Others	13	13
	Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by number of employees in their business, number of years in business operation and sector of business. It revealed that 81 respondents representing 81 percent have between 1-100 employees, 3 respondents representing 3 percent have between 101-200 employees, while 16 respondents representing 16 percent were More than 200 employees. This implies that most of the respondents have between 1-100 employees.

The table also showed that 14 respondents representing 14 percent were Less than 1 year, 22 respondents representing 22 percent were 1-3 years, 23 respondents representing 23 percent were 4-6 years, 19 respondents representing 19 percent were 7-10 years, while 22 respondents representing 22 percent were More than 10 years. Thus, majority of the respondents have been in the business for 4-6 years

The table revealed that 39% were manufacturing, 18% were services, 13% were retail, 13% were agriculture while others were 17%. This implies that majority of the respondents are manufacturers.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Ho1: Higher tax rates do not negatively affect the profitability of SMEs in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Ho2: Tax incentives do not positively influence the investment levels of SMEs Oyo State, Nigeria.

Ho3: Efficient tax administration does not enhance the growth and sustainability of SMEs.

Ho1: Higher tax rates do not negatively affect the profitability of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

H1: Higher tax rates negatively affect the profitability of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Regression Model Summary Showing the Significant Relationship between Tax Rates and Profitability of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.627	.393	.387	.551	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tax Rates

Table 3: ANOVA^A Showing the Significant Relationship between Tax Rates and Profitability of SMEs.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	19.124	1	19.124	62.879	.000b
Residual					
Total	29.502	97	.304		

	48.626	98			
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a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

b. Predictors: (Constant), Tax Rates

Table 4: Regression Coefficients Showing the Significant Relationship between Tax Rates and Profitability of SMEs.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.213	.141		1.514	.000
	Tax Policies	.217	.100	.218	2.177	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SMEs Growth

Interpretation of Result

Table 4 shows the summary of the regression analysis carried out to test hypothesis one, and the result shows a significant negative relationship between higher tax rates and the profitability of SMEs in Ibadan, (B = 0.217, $P < 0.05$), therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted.

Furthermore, table 2 and table 3 show an F statistic indicating the model's prediction strength (F = 62.879, $R^2 = 48\%$, $P < 0.05$). Conclusively, the result shows that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted because the sig.000 is less than the significance level of 0.05.

Hypothesis Two

H_0 2: Tax incentives do not positively influence the investment decisions of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

H_2 : Tax incentives positively influence the investment decisions of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Regression Model Summary Showing the Impact of Tax Incentives on the Investment Decisions of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.699 ^b	.488	.477	.509	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tax Incentives

Table 6: ANOVA^A Showing the Impact of Taxation Policies on the Growth and Performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	23.732	2	11.866	45.758	.000 ^b
Residual	24.894	96	.259		
Total	48.626	98			

a. Dependent Variable: Investment Decisions of SMEs

b. Predictors: (Constant), Tax Incentives

Table 7: Regression Coefficients Showing the Impact of Tax Incentives on the Investment Decisions of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.213	.141		1.514	.000
	Tax Incentives	.317	.095	.323	3.342	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Investment Decision of SMEs

Interpretation of Result

The Table 7 shows the summary of the regression analysis carried out to test hypothesis two, and the result indicates a significant positive relationship between tax incentives and the investment decisions of SMEs in Ibadan, (B = 0.317, P<0.05), therefore, the null hypothesis Ho2 is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis H2 is accepted.

Furthermore, Table 2 and Table 3 shows an F statistic indicating the model's prediction strength ($F = 45.758$, $R^2 = 48\%$, $P < 0.05$). Conclusively, the result shows that H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted because the sig.000 is less than the significance level of 0.05.

Hypothesis Three

H_0 : Efficient tax administration does not enhance the growth and sustainability of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

H_3 : Efficient tax administration enhances the growth and sustainability of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 8: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.716 ^a	.512	.497	.500	1.987

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tax Administration

Table 9: ANOVA^A

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	24.896	3	8.299	33.223	.000b
Residual	23.730	95	.250		
Total	48.626	98			

a. Dependent Variable: Growth and Sustainability of SMEs

b. Predictors: (Constant), Efficient Tax Administration

Table 10: Regression Coefficients Showing the Evidence of Efficient Tax Administration on the Growth and Sustainability of SMEs

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

1	(Constant)	.213	.141		1.514	.000
	SMEs Development	.315	.100	.295	3.161	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Growth and Sustainability of SMEs

Interpretation of results

Table 10 shows the summary of the regression analysis carried out to test hypothesis three, and the result shows that there is a significant positive relationship between efficient tax administration and the growth and sustainability of SMEs in Ibadan, ($B = 0.315$, $P < 0.05$), therefore, the null H_0 is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis H_3 was accepted.

Furthermore, table 2 and table 3 show an F statistic indicating the models' prediction strength ($F = 33.223$, $R^2 = 48\%$, $P < 0.05$). Conclusively, the result shows that H_0 is rejected and H_3 is accepted because the sig.000 is less than the significance level of 0.05.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings is organized according to each hypothesis tested. From the linear regression analysis conducted above, the following findings were made:

Hypothesis One - Higher tax rates negatively affect the profitability of SMEs.

The analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between higher tax rates and the profitability of SMEs in Ibadan. This finding is consistent with the theoretical expectation that higher tax burdens reduce the net income of businesses, thereby affecting their profitability. SMEs, which often operate with limited capital and tight margins, are particularly vulnerable to high tax rates. The regression results indicated that a unit increase in tax rates leads to a decrease in profitability, highlighting the sensitivity of SMEs to tax policies. In support of this finding, a study titled "The Impact of Tax Rates on the Profitability of SMEs in Pakistan" which found out that high tax rates have a detrimental effect on the profitability of SMEs in Pakistan (Memon, Channa & Abbas, 2017). Similarly, another study titled "The Effect of Corporate Taxes on Investment and Entrepreneurship" demonstrated that higher corporate tax rates negatively impact investment and entrepreneurship across various countries (Djankov, Ganser, McLiesh, Ramalho & Shleifer, 2010).

Hypothesis Two - Tax incentives positively influence the investment decisions of SMEs.

The regression analysis showed a significant positive relationship between tax incentives and the investment decisions of SMEs in Ibadan. This finding aligns with the hypothesis that tax incentives, such as deductions, credits, and allowances, can stimulate investment by reducing the effective tax burden on businesses. SMEs are likely to reinvest their tax savings into business expansion, technology adoption, and other growth-oriented activities. The positive impact of tax

incentives on investment decisions is supported by the findings of a study with the title “Tax Policy and Investment Behavior” which stated that tax incentives play a crucial role in stimulating corporate investment (Hall & Jorgenson, 1967). Firms respond positively to investment tax credits, leading to increased capital expenditure.

Hypothesis Three - Efficient tax administration enhances the growth and sustainability of SMEs.

The analysis also confirmed a significant positive relationship between efficient tax administration and the growth and sustainability of SMEs. Efficient tax administration, characterized by simplicity, transparency, and fairness, reduces the compliance burden on SMEs and minimizes the risk of tax evasion and corruption. When SMEs perceive the tax system as fair and easy to navigate, they are more likely to comply with tax regulations, which in turn support their growth and sustainability. This finding is corroborated by a study titled “Tax Policy in Emerging Countries” which emphasize that efficient and fair tax administration is essential for fostering a conducive business environment (Bird & Zolt, 2008). Similarly, another study highlights that simpler tax compliance procedures can significantly reduce the administrative burden on SMEs, thus promoting their growth (Coolidge, 2012).

The findings from this study have several important implications for policymakers, business owners, and researchers. First, the negative impact of high tax rates on SME profitability suggests that tax policies need to be carefully calibrated to support rather than hinder business growth. Second, the positive influence of tax incentives on investment decisions underscores the need for targeted tax incentives that can drive business expansion and innovation. Finally, the importance of efficient tax administration in enhancing SME growth and sustainability points to the need for continuous improvements in tax systems and practices.

For business owners, understanding the impact of tax policies on their operations can help in making informed decisions about tax planning and compliance. SMEs should actively engage with policymakers to advocate for tax policies that support their growth and address their unique challenges. For researchers, this study provides a foundation for further exploration into the relationship between taxation and SME performance. This study highlights the critical interplay between taxation policies and the growth and performance of SMEs. By adopting supportive tax policies and ensuring efficient tax administration, governments can create a favorable environment that promotes the development and sustainability of SMEs, ultimately contributing to broader economic growth and development.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the impact of taxation policies on the growth and performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria by evaluating primary data gathered from Ibadan SMEs owners. According to the findings, it was revealed that there is a significant effect of Tax Policies on the growth and performance of SMEs in Ibadan, Nigeria. As a result, the study concluded that there is a significant relationship between taxation policies and the growth of SMEs in Ibadan.

This study has been able to discover a lot of things during its findings in which the discovery of taxation policies significantly influences the growth and performance of SMEs in Ibadan. Nevertheless, This study offers the following recommendation:

- i. Tax regulations governing SMEs should be simplified in order to make compliance easier for them. This includes clear and simple tax regulations, and an undemanding tax filing process.
- ii. Provide educational programs and workshops to help SMEs understand their tax obligations and navigate the tax system effectively.
- iii. Since tax paid is an important determinant of the growth of small and medium scale businesses in Oyo State, the tax collected from businesses should be judiciously used for the betterment of the masses because that will encourage the taxpayers to continue with their civic responsibility. The well-to-do in Oyo State community should make funds available to the needy potential business-men and women so as to supplement government effort in reducing unemployment.
- iv. The ‘ability to pay’ of every SME should be given priority consideration before the payment burden is placed on the SME. Particularly as the expansion and contribution of the SME are greatly dependent on her cash inflows, profitability and reinvestment, the lesser the financial burden on SME, the better the chances of profitability, reinvestment and expansion of the SME and the better the national economy.

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